

B-WaterSmart dashboard – Early release

Deliverable 3.6

B-WaterSmart dashboard – Early release

D3.6: B-WaterSmart dashboard – Early release
Document accompanying the tool

Summary

The B-WaterSmart dashboard (early release) is a web application that uses the B-WaterSmart Assessment Framework (as described in our deliverable D6.3) to support the strategic planning process of decision-makers in the water-sector with the objective to assess gains in the road towards a water-smart(-er) society. Within the B-WaterSmart project, the dashboard is going to be used by the Living Labs (e.g., water utilities, municipalities) as a management support tool in the coming period within the context of the Innovation Alliance (T1.4). The early release of the dashboard together with this accompanying document form the groundwork for these activities. In the current early release of the dashboard, the main functionalities include user authentication and authorization, the creation of new assessments regarding water-smartness, and the review of previously made assessments and generation of scenarios. Setting up the assessment, allows for selection of strategic objectives, assessment criteria and selected metrics of the B-WaterSmart Assessment Framework and performing the initial analysis, based on the default reference values. The possibility of targets setting and alternatives analysis is currently ongoing work with selected draft mockups being presented in this document. The dashboard is building on a combination of FIWARE technology and relational data management systems for the persistence of dashboard related data. The functionalities and technologies used will be enriched and expanded in the beta version of the tool with final delivery date in August 2024 (D3.7).

Deliverable number	Work package
D3.6	WP3
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Planned delivery date	Actual delivery date
31/08/2023	24/12/2023

Dissemination level

- PU = Public**
- PP = Restricted to other programme participants
- RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium.
Please specify: _____
- CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium

Document version

Date	Change
31/08/2023	Initial version
24/12/2023	Version 2: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• An executive summary was added.• Added headers & footers and fixed formatting according to other deliverables.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AC	Assessment Criteria
AF	Assessment Framework
BWS	B-WaterSmart
Dx.y	Deliverable y of WPx
InAll	Innovation Alliance
LL	Living Labs
SO	Strategic Objective
Tx.y	Task y of WPx
WPx	Work Package x
UI	User Interface
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSG	Static Site Generation
SSR	Server-Side Reading

Executive Summary

The B-WaterSmart Dashboard, formerly known as the Water-smartness Dashboard, is a critical component of the B-WaterSmart project's strategic planning and assessment framework. The deliverable, D3.6, signifies the early release of the web application, with a final release (D3.7) expected in August 2024. A shift in terminology from "water-smartness" to "B-WaterSmart" aligns with the project's branding strategy while maintaining content consistency. D3.6 serves as an early version for the B-WaterSmart Dashboard, catering to the BWS consortium, specifically B-WaterSmart Living Labs and InAll partners. The report is designed to guide users and potential reviewers, offering insights into the tool's functionalities. As development progresses, the audience will expand to include regional decision-makers, authorities, researchers, and consultants. The dashboard leverages the B-WaterSmart assessment framework, developed in Work Package 6 (WP6), deploying it into online tool. The collaboration between WP6, but also WP1 with T3.9 ensured a seamless alignment with the project's objectives. Technical development employs FIWARE technology, Stellio NGSI-LD context broker, and a combination of UI/UX tools. The architecture involves Next.js, SQL, and Stellio, hosted within ICCS's cloud infrastructure. The early version of the dashboard follows the B-WaterSmart Assessment Framework's structure, facilitating the selection of Strategic Objectives, Assessment Criteria, and metrics for assessments. The strategic planning process, encompassing six steps, prioritizes steps 1-4 in the initial release. Users can sign up, create, and assess scenarios based on chosen metrics. The report provides a comprehensive overview of the dashboard's functionalities through screenshots and explanations. Future developments involve continued implementation of BWS AF functionalities, and training sessions. Deliverable 3.6 provides access to the early version of the B-WaterSmart Dashboard, offering a glimpse into its functionalities and the ongoing development process.

1 Introduction

This report together with the tool available at <https://bws-dashboard.iccs.gr/> constitutes the B-WaterSmart project's *Deliverable 3.6 B-WaterSmart dashboard – Early release*, previously called D3.6 *Water-smartness dashboard – Early release*. The D3.6 is an outcome of the T3.9, which develops an online dashboard deploying the B-WaterSmart assessment framework developed in WP6 “to support strategic planning and to assess gains in the process of achieving long-term objectives towards a water-smart(-er) society”, as specified in D6.3. The current deliverable covers the early version of the tool, which will be followed by *D3.7 Water-smartness dashboard – Final release* due in M48 of the project, namely August 2024.

1.1 Disclaimer about terminology and deliverable title

In deviation from the title of the deliverable and the tool as given in the Grant Agreement, it was decided that the name “water-smartness dashboard” will be replaced by “**B-WaterSmart dashboard**”. This is in line with the project’s dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy that aims to establish a clearly recognizable brand of the project. The tool developed by T3.9, is therefore referred to as B-WaterSmart dashboard from now on. The content and scope of the deliverable remain completely unchanged and fully in line with the definition in the Grant Agreement. Consequently, the following deliverable titles are used: D3.6 *B-WaterSmart dashboard – Early release* and D3.7 *B-WaterSmart dashboard– Final release* (due in M48).

1.2 Purpose of the report and intended audience

The actual deliverable D3.6 is the early release of the web-application “B-WaterSmart dashboard”, accessible via <https://bws-dashboard.iccs.gr/>. This report is provided as a supplementary item for the convenience of current users and potential reviewers of the dashboard. The purpose of this document is to present the early version of dashboard and its main functionalities. Additionally, the report and especially *Section 3* might serve as a first version of a user manual. The intended audience of this document is the BWS consortium, especially B-WaterSmart Living Labs (LLs) and other partners involved in T1.4 *Implementing the B-WaterSmart innovation alliance InAll*. InAll will be the first users of the dashboard with the exact schedule to be defined.

It is however intended, that as the dashboard evolves towards the final version, the audience and interested groups of users of the tool will expand beyond BWS project members, including regional strategic decision-makers, European and national authorities, researchers, and consultants. Those are the main groups of users of the BWS Assessment Framework as defined in the D6.3, and therefore the dashboard is aiming to address those groups of users as well. On the other hand, the D3.6 is a public deliverable and therefore anyone interested is welcome to register and use the tool.

1.3 Structure of the report

The document presents the process leading to the dashboard creation from the conceptual and technical point of view. This is followed by the presentation of the early version of the tool; including architecture, features and main elements and explanation of the next steps concerning dashboard use within the project and the development. The report includes also a short description of the work done in relation to the recommendations received from SINTEF and LNEC.

2 Methodology

2.1 The road to the dashboard

The dashboard deploys the B-WaterSmart assessment framework, which is the outcome of the work performed in WP6 led by SINTEF, according to the D6.3. The dashboard uses advanced visualizing techniques and presents the information in a user-friendly and intuitive way. To ensure that the ICCS team, leading the dashboard development, is well acquainted with the progress and outcome of the WP6 work, interactions between WP6 and T3.9 were initiated from the beginning of the project. ICCS was actively participating in WP6 meetings, and also participated in the internal quality assurance review of deliverables D6.2 *The water-smartness assessment framework (V1)* and D6.3 *Final version of the water-smartness assessment framework*. On the other hand, interconnections with WP1, including the participation of ICCS in T1.4 were identified of importance for the dashboard development. The dashboard will be used to support strategic planning as a part of InAll activities performed in T1.4. Additionally, LNEC, who is leading task 1.4 was responsible for the process of collecting/providing feedback for the V2 of the Assessment Framework and is the leader of the D1.3 *Recommendations for refinement of the water-smartness framework and its transformation into a dashboard-type software*. ICCS was following the developments in WP1 as well, through participation in relevant meetings. To ensure that ICCS, as T3.9 leader, has the adequate level of understanding of the framework and strategic planning process, two online meetings with LNEC and SINTEF were organized by ICCS towards the final stage of the framework development. The first meeting was held in November 2022, the latter in February 2023. As a basis for discussion the following documents were used: D6.2 – working version, D6.3 and especially D1.3 with special focus on the *Section 4.2 Recommendations for transformation of the water-smartness framework into a dashboard-type software*. As a result, a number of recommendations in relation to the dashboard were discussed. During the period February – July 2023 *ad hoc* communication with teams of LNEC and SINTEF was taking place in parallel to the dashboard development, whenever such need arose. Also, the LNEC team has provided a document with some examples for metric normalization, which was used for AC normalization. LNEC has presented the AWARE-P tool (Coelho et al. 2013), which served as inspiration in relation to the BWS framework, as described in D6.1, and some tool elements, mainly related to visualization in the early version of the tool, as suggested.

2.2 Technical development

The dashboard is building on a combination of FIWARE technology and relational data management systems for the persistence of dashboard related data. The basic FIWARE component used is the FIWARE compatible Stellio NGSI-LD context broker. That allows to store and show essential data regarding metrics as described by NGSI-LD semantics. An initial analysis of the following UI/UX tools has been performed: Kurento, Knowage, Wirecloud, Tableau and Infogram. The last two have been identified as of possible interest. Their incorporation will be considered for the final version of the dashboard combined with the tailor-made next.js based web application which hosts the component. In terms of compliance with other BWS tools this has also been analyzed; the use of Digital Enabler has been discussed with ENG followed by a decision for following custom approach in the current version of the dashboard. The Baseform tool has not been considered at this point, as it is not FIWARE compliant, but this possibility will be reviewed in the coming period.

3 Dashboard – early version

3.1 The approach for the alpha version of the dashboard

The BWS dashboard implements digitally the B-WaterSmart Assessment Framework (BWS AF) using the tree structure, as defined in D6.3, where strategic objectives split into assessment criteria, which in turn are supported by metrics. In the dashboard, this structure is preserved allowing the user to choose Strategic Objectives (SO), Assessment Criteria (AC) and the metrics of interest for the assessments. Moreover, the dashboard will be used to support the strategic planning process for achieving the water-smartness and described by Ugarelli et al., 2021. The strategic planning process encompasses an iterative approach build by 6 steps: Step 1 – Selection of strategic objectives, assessment criteria, metrics and reference values, Step 2 – Diagnosis, including scenarios creation, Step 3 - Set the targets, Step 4 – Develop the strategic plan, Step 5 - Implement the strategic plan, Step 6 - Monitor performance. The implementation of steps 1-4 was given priority in the process of the dashboard development, with steps 1 and 2 available in the early version. For scenarios and steps 3-5 draft mockups have been created with the backend implementation currently ongoing. Step 5 concerns the activities taking place outside of the dashboard environment, while Step 6 concerns performance monitoring, which will be considered for the final version of the tool, according to the needs. The structure of the tool in this and following version is attempting to reflect the deployment methodology as described in D6.3.

3.2 Dashboard – early version presentation

The user of the early version of the dashboard has the possibility to perform an assessment based on the metrics to be selected from the selection of metrics of the BWS AF. The user is not obliged to complete all the steps and can save the work at any moment to continue later. The available functionalities are presented in this section using screenshots from the early version of the tool. The values included in the figures are for presentational purposes only.

The tool is available at <https://bws-dashboard.iccs.gr/>. The following credentials are needed to access the tool:

Username: iccs

Password: iccsBWS

In order to start using the tool, the user needs to sign up/sign in. The dashboard Sign in page is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Sign in page

The assessment page is presented in Figure 2. Under “Assessments” the user has access to the previous assessments with the possibility grouping the assessments based on SO, AC, metrics used.

Figure 2: Assessments page

The user can create a new assessment by clicking “New assessment” in the top left corner. When “New assessment” is chosen, the user is asked to give it a title, and has an option of adding a description and in the future also an image (Figure 4). After pressing “Save and next” the user can

start the process of the Assessment set up. This step consists of choosing SOs (Figure 5), ACs (Figure 5.6), and Metrics (Figure 5.7).
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6), and metrics (Figure 7). For each SO a description is provided by clicking on the button “i” as provided in D6.3. The description for AC and metrics will follow in next version of the tool.

Figure 3: New assessment creation

Figure 4: Strategic objectives selection

Figure 5: Assessment criteria selection

Figure 6: Metrics selection

Once the assessment is set up, the user can proceed to the diagnosis step which allows to calculate the outputs for metrics and to assess results. The user is requested to provide input values and the output values are calculated with the result judgment visible. Judgement is based on the reference values as defined in the D6.3 (Figure 8). In the current version the reference values cannot be modified. The equation for calculation of each metric, and the respective variables needed, are presented.

Figure 7: Results per metric based on the reference values

Having filled in all the values for all the selected metrics the user has the option to see the results per metric, assessment criteria and strategic objective (Figure 9). The results of the assessment criteria are normalized considering the reference values of each metric and equal weights. In the current version the SO values are an arithmetic mean of AC values.

Figure 8: The results per metric, AC, SO

After reaching this step, the user is able to proceed with the assessment by creating scenarios for previously selected metrics and define expected trends for each of them, based on external factor(s).

Figure 9: Scenarios page where user defines the expected trend per metric.

The draft mockups for the next steps: targets setting, analyzing alternatives are presented in section 4.2.

3.3 Architecture

The dashboard comprises several architectural layers, providing the necessary functionality to the dashboard. The persistence layer stores all necessary information, the business logic performs the main processing functions and finally the user interface (UI) visualizes the related information.

Functionalities of the system, include user authentication and authorization, the creation of new assessments and the review of previously made assessments. The aforementioned functionality is supported by the various layers of the system by using several standardized interfaces and API's which are engineered according to the client-server paradigm. The following diagram (Figure 10) summarizes the architectural view of the system.

Figure 10: BWS dashboard architecture and technologies

The technology stack used to support the aforementioned architecture includes the following

- Next.js
- SQL
- Stellio

Next.js is a popular and powerful React framework for building web applications. It is designed to make server-side rendering (SSR) and static site generation (SSG) straightforward, providing developers with an efficient and enjoyable development experience. SQL (Structured Query Language) databases are widely used to manage and store structured data efficiently and securely. They are based on the relational model, which means that data is organized into tables with rows and columns. Each row represents a record or an entity, while columns represent attributes or characteristics of those entities. Stellio is an NGSI-LD compliant context **broker** developed by EGM. NGSI-LD is an Open API and Datamodel specification for **context** management published by ETSI.

The overall system is hosted within ICCS's premises cloud infrastructure which is based on the proxmox virtualization system. Figure 11 summarizes the execution environment of the web application.

Figure 11: BWS dashboard system deployment technologies

As can be seen in the Figure 11, the system is deployed on a proxmox based, headless Ubuntu Operating System, which hosts the NEXT.js runtime environment in one hand and additionally comprises a containerized docker environment that hosts all the required components of the Stello context broker.

3.4 Work progress in relation to recommendations from WP1 and WP6

As discussed in the section 2.1 *The road to the dashboard*, the dashboard is building on the work within the BWS project performed until now. The analysis of the deployment level in terms of Section 4.2 *Recommendations for transformation of the water-smartness framework into a dashboard-type software* of the D1.3 is available in Appendix A. Concerning the recommendations presented in the D6.2 in section 9 *The FAST application* following conclusions can be drawn.

The dashboard application shares some common characteristics with the FAST application and has also incorporated some aspects according to the analysis performed in the 9.3 “Lessons learned” chapter of D6.2

The dashboard app has been also developed in a typed language and follows paradigms of Object-Oriented programming such as the use of interfaces and flexible data models, therefore providing transparency and ease of extension both in terms of data model and processing.

A feature which has been added is for end users to have the possibility of saving an assessment in draft form in order to continue editing at a latter instance of time or alternatively complete the assessment, save it, and continue with the subsequent aspects of the application. This functionality controls when a functionality is saved, therefore giving the possibility to two users using the same account to co-operate when editing a given assessment. Moreover, regarding the data model, all object entities have linked in a unique manner as proposed by the recommendation of linking “answers to questions” in D6.2, thus data is linked in a manner which is not affected by issues such as “switching” metrics.

Additionally, the way of presenting the result per metric in relation to the (in current version) predefined reference values has been approached in a more intuitive way.

4 Next steps

4.1 Dashboard use in BWS

Task T3.9 will continue implementing the functionalities of the BWS AF into the dashboard. ICCS will also organize a meeting with LNEC, the leader of T1.4, to plan the next steps in relation to use of the dashboard by InAll. Additionally, in cooperation with LNEC, an online training has been scheduled, as a part of InAll Phase 4 meeting. It has been arranged that in the autumn of 2023 (estimated for November), the tool will be tested by the SINTEF team to provide feedback and ideas for improvements towards the final version of the tool.

Additionally, another training is planned to be organized, under the framework of T1.3 in collaboration with SINTEF. That training will be intended for a larger audience, trying to attract stakeholders also outside of the BWS consortium. Its initial date has been discussed for June 2024.

4.2 Development

The draft mockups for the next steps of the strategic planning to be implemented are under development and some initial versions can be seen in Figures 12-15. The visualization of alternatives was inspired by those of AWARE-P (Coelho et al. 2013) presented by LNEC with further adjustments in the context of strategic planning for BWS specifically to be discussed. The possibility of cooperation in terms of possible link with Baseform tool will be investigated as their tool for decision support also uses this type of visualization (D3.4 *The monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit – Final release, tool #17*)

Please note that reference values used in all the mockups are indicative. For actual values please check D6.3.

Figure 12. Target setting per metric (draft mockup)

Figure 13: Alternatives creation page (draft mockup)

Figure 14. Alternatives analysis page (draft mockup)

Also, the page summarizing the results and facilitating development of the strategic plan is under construction (Figure 16).

Figure 15: Summary page (draft mockup)

In the beta version of the dashboard the currently existing features will be enhanced, and others will be added. Some of those features are the possibility of adding new metrics, the possibility of choosing services-based assessment, metrics aggregation/ disaggregation, the possibility to modify the reference values, the description of AC and metrics. The summary showing progress versus recommendations presented in D1.3 is shown in Appendix A. The possibility of adding commercial visualization tools (e.g. Tableau, Infogram) will be considered for the final version of the tool. Also, possibility of incorporation of other tools will be reexamined, if needed.

5 Conclusions

The present deliverable shows the early version of the B-WaterSmart dashboard developed within the B-WaterSmart project. This is accomplished through providing access to the tool and presenting the accompanying document. Section 3.2 of this document can serve also as a user manual for the early version of the dashboard. The main features and functionalities are shown using screenshots. The initial mockups are also used to give a feeling of the work that will follow towards the development of the final version of the tool. Additionally, the document provides insights into the process of dashboard creation from the conceptual and technical point of view, the architecture, and next steps.

6 References

Cardoso, M.A., et al. (2022). Recommendations for refinement of the water-smartness framework and its transformation into a dashboard-type software. H2020 B-WaterSmart Deliverable Deliverable D1.3.

Coelho, S.T., Vitorino, D., Alegre H., (2013) AWARE-P: a system-based software for urban water IAM planning, LESAM 2013, Sydney, Australia, 10-12 September 2013

Silva, C. et al. (2023) Final version of the water-smartness assessment framework, H2020 B-WaterSmart Deliverable D6.3

Santos Clotas E. et al. (2023) The monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit – Final release H2020 B-WaterSmart Deliverable D3.4

Ugarelli, R., et al. (2021). What is water-smartness and how to assess it. H2020 B-WaterSmart Deliverable D6.1. <https://b-watersmart.eu/download/what-is-water-smartness-and-how-to-asses-it-d6-1/>

Ugarelli, R. et al. (2022). The water-smartness assessment framework (V1). H2020 B-WaterSmart Deliverable D6.2.

Appendix A. Recommendations presented in D1.3 and their level of deployment in the early version of the dashboard

Recommendation from D1.3	Level of deployment
Include the name of the metric in the selection panel (in addition to the code)	Available in early version
Allow to visualize the results for the different strategic objectives.	Available in early version
Visualize the judgement of each metric based on the reference values defined for good, fair, and poor performance	Available in early version
Metric normalization based on the judgement defined	Available in early version
Prospective evaluation for different scenarios	Available in early version
Visualize the strategic assessment on a temporal basis (metric computation for different years)	Partially available in early version
Include the possibility of disaggregate the metrics as needed	Ongoing work
Include the possibility to define other metrics (not included in the AF);	Ongoing work
Include the default reference values in the dashboard, that the LLI may adjust based on validated best practices;	Ongoing work
For potential aggregation exercises, include the possibility to associate different weights for each metric in relation to their importance for the LLI, an issue to be further analysed in T1.4	Ongoing work
Allow to visualize the results from different points of view/dimensions: social, environmental, economic, technical and governance	Ongoing work
The possibility to establish targets for strategic planning horizon (tN) and intermediate targets for the evaluation of system performance – an essential basis for establishing the diagnosis, prioritizing intervention solutions, and monitoring the results	Ongoing work
Compare different alternatives	Ongoing work
Automatically import to the dashboard the input values, e.g., from an excel file;	To be investigated
Improve the normalization method of the metrics' results (included in FAST)	To be investigated
Identify the input variables needed; for each input variables, identify the selected metrics it is used for, ensure that each variable is	To be investigated

inputted only once, regardless of the number of metrics it is used for;, To be investigated	
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869171. The publication reflects only the authors' views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.